

Pregnancy Characteristics and Delivery Outcomes of Individual Mother Hospitalized at Jalalabad, Kyrgyzstan

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Abstract:

Background: Maternal morbidity is a silent struggle, echoing the untold stories of resilience and strength in the face of adversity. Women of childbearing age are faced with extreme uncertainties; hence the purpose of this study was to analyze fertility trend and maternal complications including the possible high-risk factors connected to maternal morbidity. Maternal morbidity could be prevented through early detection, including the period preceding pregnancy.

Methods and methodology: This is a retrospective cross-sectional study using data from hospital database describes trends of fertility and with immediate post-delivery maternal complication. The data

was collected just from month January in 2023 from a Regional Maternity Hospital in Jalalabad, Kyrgyzstan. Total of 260 sample were drawn from the data base for the study.

Objective: The study intended to find the different pregnancy characteristics and the outcomes of delivery of Individual mother who were Hospitalized at Jalalabad, Kyrgyzstan. We settled for this topic because it is one of the significant causes of death among reproductive age group women around the world.

Result: Among 260 delivery cases, majority 56.2% of them were from age group 21 - 25 years. Majority of them have more than one child and 22.7% cases had more than 3 children. Common complications associated during pregnancy were anemia (17.3%) & Pre-eclampsia (16.1%) whereas most common

postpartum complication was PPH associated with atony (17.3%). Obesity (10%) and Pre-existing hypertension (9.6%) were the most common comorbidity associated with pregnancy.

Conclusion: The research population appears to have high fertility trends. The main causes of obstetric complications were anemia, hypertension, and postpartum hemorrhage. Two prevalent comorbidities linked to pregnancy were obesity and underlying hypertension. To reduce pregnancy-related problems, it is imperative that interventions be implemented that support early ANC attendance, lower obesity, increase access to blood pressure monitoring, and provide family planning information and services.

Keywords: *Trend, Fertility, Morbidity, Postpartum, Early.*

Introduction

Maternal morbidity is not just a health crisis; it's a call for societies to prioritize and safeguard the wellbeing of the women who bring life into the world. World health organization (WHO) has defined maternal morbidity as:

Any health condition attributed to and/or complicating pregnancy, and childbirth that has a negative impact on the woman's well-being and/or functioning (WHO, 2019).

There are ongoing efforts to develop and validate tools to measure maternal morbidity.

About 140 million births take place every year and the proportion attended by skilled health personnel has increased: from 58% in 1990 to 81% in 2019. This is mostly due to larger numbers of births taking place at a health facility. Deaths from complications during pregnancy, childbirth, and the postnatal period have declined by 38% in the last two decades, but at an average reduction of just under 3% per year, this pace of progress is far too slow (WHO, 2019).

Potential risk factors of maternal mortality or morbidity, includes pulmonary hypertension, placenta previa, sickle cell disease, gestational hypertension, mild or unspecified preeclampsia, severe preeclampsia, chronic kidney disease, preexisting hypertension, chronic ischemic heart disease, congenital heart disease, systemic lupus erythematosus, HIV, multiple gestation, substance use disorder, alcohol abuse, tobacco use, cardiac valvular disease, chronic congestive heart failure, asthma, preexisting diabetes, gestational diabetes, obesity, cystic fibrosis, and

previous cesarean delivery. These causes are largely preventable and treatable but certain regions lack the necessary access to high quality healthcare (Fink, et al., 2023).

Preventing maternal morbidity is crucial for ensuring the well-being of pregnant women and reducing adverse health outcomes. Access to quality antenatal care plays a pivotal role in early detection and management of potential complications. Timely and skilled obstetric care, including safe delivery practices, can significantly reduce the risk of maternal morbidity.

The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) offers an opportunity for the international community to work together and accelerate progress to improve maternal health for all women, in all countries, under all circumstances. SDG targets for maternal health include 3.1, aiming for an average global ratio of less than 70 deaths per 100 000 births by 2030, and 3.8, calling for the achievement of universal health coverage. These cannot be achieved without reproductive, maternal, newborn and child health coverage for all (WHO, UNICEF, UNFPA, The World Bank Group and the United Nations Population Division, 2023).

There are Various advanced technologies such as cardiotocography, color Doppler, biophysical profile are utilized in labour wards, contributing to the rising rates of caesarian sections alongside other medical factors associated with pregnancy (Rao, & Rampure, 2013).

Other contributing factors to the increase in caesarian section rates in grand multiparas include better identification of high-risk pregnancies through improved antenatal care, a

growing trend towards elective induction of labor, a decrease in operative vaginal deliveries due to various complications, a reduction in vaginal breech deliveries, and an overall rise in the number of procedures performed (Desai, et al., 2013).

A Caesarian Section (CS) is seen as a safer option than a prolonged and difficult vaginal operative delivery to decrease maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality (Jacob, & Bhargava, 2012).

Methods and Methodology

A total of 260 sample were drawn from the data base of just a month- January 2023 for the study. Information of the respondent were collected by the record file of patient from the hospital. It was a retrospective cross-sectional study using data from hospital database describes trends of fertility and with immediate post-delivery maternal complication.

Result

There were total 260 delivery cases that had occurred for the month of January, 2023. The data that we have collected from the maternity hospitals consists of both working and non-working women. The results of the data collected for our study are as follows (see Table 1).

Table 1. Distribution of Respondent According to Their Age

Responses	Frequency (n=260)	Percentage (%)
15 - 20 Year	35	13.5
21-25 Year	146	56.2
26 - 30 Year	53	20.4
31 - 35 Year	19	7.3
36 - 40 year	7	2.7

Above table shows that majority 56.2% of the women were from age group 21 - 25 years followed by 20.4% of them were in age group 26-30 years. Remaining 13.5% and 7.3% were in between age group 15-20 years and 31-35 years

respectively. The mean age was 23 ± 2 years (Table 1).

Table 2. Distribution of Respondent According to Their Occupation

Responses	Frequency (n=260)	Percentage (%)
Teacher	14	5.4
Doctor	32	12.3
Housewife	199	76.5
Others	15	5.8

Above table shows that majority 76.5% (199) of respondents were housewife remaining 12.3% were doctors and 5.4% were working as a teacher similarly out of remaining 5.8% said some of them they were layer, and others work in a departmental store.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents According to the Number of Pregnancy (Gravida)

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
1-3	178	68.5
4-6	59	22.7
7	23	8.8

Above table shows that 63% of the women were pregnancy for 1-3 times, 22.7% said they were pregnant for 4-6 times, remaining 8.8% were pregnant for 7 times.

Figure 1. Distribution of Respondents According to the Mode of Delivery of Recent Pregnancy

The mode of delivery for 76.5% of the pregnancies was normal vaginal delivery followed by 19.4% were C-sections and about 2% were instrumental deliveries (Figure 1).

Table 4. Distribution of Respondents According to Maternal Complication Related to Pregnancy

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	81	31.15%
Twin Pregnancy	18	6.92%
Gestational Hypertension	24	9.2%
Anemia (1 degree)	45	17.3%
Placenta previa	6	2.3%
Pre-eclampsia	42	16.1%
Severe Pre-eclampsia	15	5.7%
Varicose veins of the lower extremities and external genitalia	15	5.7%
Partial abruption of the normally located placenta	14	5.3%

Above table shows 81 respondents have a normal pregnancy status. 18 respondents, accounting for 6.9% of the total, are experiencing a twin pregnancy. 24 respondents (9.2%) are facing gestational hypertension. Anemia (1 degree), 45 respondents (17.3%) are dealing with first-degree anemia during their pregnancy. 6 respondents (2.3%) have placenta previa. 42 respondents (16.1%) are diagnosed with pre-eclampsia. 15 respondents (5.7%) have a severe form of pre-eclampsia. 15 respondents (5.7%) are experiencing varicose veins in the lower extremities and external genitalia. Partial Abruption of the Normally Located Placenta: 14 respondents (5.3%) are dealing with partial abruption of the normally located placenta.

The most common presentation is cephalic presentation which is 244 in terms of frequency which makes it 93.8% of the total but it serves as a baseline for comparison. 8 respondents (3.1%) are experiencing a breech presentation for their first fetus. 7 respondents (2.7%) have a situation where the fetus is presenting with the feet first. 1 respondent (0.4%) is facing the complication of shoulder dystocia during pregnancy.

Table 5. Distribution of Respondents According to Their Present Pregnancy Status

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Presentation/Lie of fetus		
Cephalic presentation	244	93.8%
Breech presentation of 1st fetus,	8	3.1%
Foot presentation of the fetus,	7	2.7%
Shoulder dystocia	1	0.4%

Table 6. Distribution of Respondents According to Complication During Labour and Immediate Post Partum Period

Responses	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	194	74.61%
Perineal tear 1 degree	12	4.61%
Entwining of the umbilical cord around the fetus	9	3.4 %
Hemorrhage (Atony)	45	17.3%

This table describes about the, Maternal Condition: 194 respondents (74.61%) had normal maternal conditions. 45 respondents (17.3%) experienced PPH due to Atony. 9 respondents (3.4 %) experienced with the umbilical cord being entwined around the fetus. 12 respondents (4.4%) experienced PPH due to a first-degree perineal tear.

Table 7. Distribution of Respondents According to the Comorbid and Risk Factors of Pregnant Women

Risk factors	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	146	56.1%
Pre-existing hypertension	25	9.6%
Alcohol Abuse	21	8.0%
Tobacco Use	18	6.9%
Asthma	12	4.6%
Pre-existing diabetes	12	4.6%
Obesity	26	10%

This table shows that 25 respondents (9.6%) have pre-existing hypertension as a risk factor during pregnancy. 21 respondents (8.0%) are

identified with alcohol abuse as a risk factor. 18 respondents (6.9%) engage in tobacco use during their pregnancy. 12 respondents (4.6%) have asthma as a comorbid condition. 12 respondents (4.6%) are dealing with pre-existing diabetes as a risk factor. 26 respondents (10%) are categorized as obese, representing a risk factor during pregnancy.

Discussion

According to our study, the majority of the women (56.2%) belonged to the 21–25 age group, with a mean age of 23 ± 2 years. 13.5% of females were teenage (15–20 years) mothers. According to a UNCEF research, the mean age of pregnancy in Central Asian nations, such as Uzbekistan, is similar at 23.5 years, but the mean age of pregnancy in Western countries is greater at over 30 years (United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, n.d.). Among the respondent, majority 76.5% (199) of them were housewife. WHO states that every year, an estimated 21 million girls aged 15–19 years in developing regions become pregnant and approximately 12 million of them give birth. Pregnancies and births among adolescents are caused by a number of circumstances. First of all, girls face pressure to get married and start families in many communities. Second, because motherhood is highly regarded and females have little opportunities for education and jobs, many of them decide to become pregnant. When attempting to access contraception, they could potentially encounter stigma. Health workers' prejudice and/or unwillingness to recognize the needs of teenagers in terms of their sexual health are frequently coupled with this (WHO, 2024).

According to our survey, 8.8% of the women had become pregnant more than six times, while 63% of the women had become pregnant one to three times. Similar findings were found in an Indonesian study, where the majority of participants were multigravida and just 3% were grand multigravida (Sulastri, et al., 2019). In Kyrgyzstan, the fertility rate is 3.28, and variables that contribute to this include early marriage age, close spacing between births, low contraceptive use, and lower educational status.

Normal vaginal birth was the mode of delivery for 76.5% of the pregnancies, followed by C-sections (19.4%). When compared to the Asian study report, C-section rate of 27.3%, our analysis reveals a declining trend (Lumbiganon, et al., 2010). The results also align with a research conducted in Sweden, where the majority of babies were delivered vaginally (only 5% via scheduled delivery, 14% by emergency c-section) (Ögge, et al., 2022).

According to our research, anemia (17.3%) was the most prevalent pregnancy-related complication, followed by pre-eclampsia (16.1%), whereas PPH due to atony (17.3%) was the most common postpartum complication. PPH was managed by standard protocol and no mortality was recorded due to PPH. An Ethiopian study found that the main causes of severe obstetric complications and maternal death were eclampsia, severe anemia, and obstetric hemorrhage (Tura, et al., 2024). According to cross-sectional research by Worku et al., (2023) the most frequent pregnancy-related problems were severe headaches (pre-eclampsia) and vaginal bleeding.

High gravida, inadequate pregnancy planning, and restricted access to information on a safe pregnancy might be the cause of the high prevalence of pregnancy-related problems seen in our study. Research suggests that a high gravidity and/or is linked to difficulties during pregnancy. Compared to women who had never given birth, individuals with a parity larger than three were more likely to experience pregnancy-related problems. There is evidence that a rise in birthrate corresponds with an elevated risk of difficulties associated to pregnancy.

Further research suggests that parity raises the risk of uterine atony-induced postpartum hemorrhage, eclampsia, abruption placentae, placenta previa, anemia, and uterine rupture (Tamale, et al., 2022). The results of this study show that more family planning information and services should be available, and that women need to be made more aware of the risks associated with having several children.

According to our research, the two most prevalent comorbidities linked to pregnancy

were obesity (10%) and pre-existing hypertension (9.6%). According to Partick SR, there is a correlation between obesity and pregnancy-related difficulties, and the likelihood of these issues increases as the condition worsens. Maternal obesity or overweight is thought to be responsible for 25% of pregnancy problems, including large for gestational age infants, premature births, prenatal hypertension, preeclampsia, and gestational diabetes (Ramsey, & Schenken, 2024).

Conclusion and Recommendations

A notable trend of high fertility rates was seen in the research population, suggesting a tendency toward higher reproductive activity within the community. In spite of this increased fertility, good delivery outcomes were noted, indicating that the healthcare system or implemented treatments successfully managed the pregnancies to successful ends. The three main causes of severe obstetric complications were anemia, hypertension, and postpartum hemorrhage. Pregnancy was frequently correlated with obesity and pre-existing hypertension. Pregnancy-related problems can thus be prevented in large part by implementing programs that support early ANC attendance, reducing obesity, increase access to blood pressure monitoring, and provide family planning information and services.

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